

Supplementary Material

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Additional file 2: Table S1. GenBank accession number and list of *Anaplasma phagocyto philum* nucleotide sequences obtained from GB livestock, *I. ricinus* and deer species.

Sequence_ID	Accession_number
A.pha./f/I.ric-M13.2/GB	OQ436965
A.pha./f/I.ric-M13.3/GB	OQ436966
A.pha./f/I.ric-Pem-6-2021/GB	OQ436967
A.pha./f/I.ric-Pem-7-2021/GB	OQ436968
A.pha./h1/B.tau-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436969
A.pha./h2/B.tau-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436970
A.pha./n1/I.ric-Cor-2021/GB	OQ436971
A.pha./n2/I.ric-Cor-2021/GB	OQ436972
A.pha./O.ar-100857-Dor-2021/GB	OQ436973
A.pha/B.tau-C315970-2023/GB	OQ436974
A.pha/B.tau-C316672-2023/GB	OQ436975
A.pha/B.tau-C316675-2023/GB	OQ436976
A.pha/C.cap-M0404-2023/GB	OQ436977
A.pha/C.cap-M413-2021/GB	OQ436978
A.pha/C._ela-Nor405-2021/GB	OQ436979
A.pha/C.ela-Nor408-2021/GB	OQ436980
A.pha/f.I.ric/n=5/Cod-29-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436981
A.pha/f.I.ric/n_5/Cod-5-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436982
A.pha/f/B.tau-32b-2023/GB	OQ436983
A.pha/f/B.tau-089-2023/GB	OQ436984
A.pha/f/B.tau-103-Cor-2021/GB	OQ436985
A.pha/f/B.tau-169b-2023/GB	OQ436986
A.pha/f/B.tau-229b-2023/GB	OQ436987
A.pha/f/B.tau-255-2023/GB	OQ436988
A.pha/f/B.tau-292d-2023/GB	OQ436989
A.pha/f/B.tau-308-2023/GB	OQ436990
A.pha/f/b.tau-309b-2023/GB	OQ436991
A.pha/f/b.tau-329-2023/GB	OQ436992
A.pha/f/B.tau-343b-2023/GB	OQ436993
A.pha/f/B.tau-343c-2023/GB	OQ436994
A.pha/f/B.tau-483-2021/GB	OQ436995
A.pha/f/B.tau-316672-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436996
A.pha/f/B.tau-317934-2023/GB	OQ436997
A.pha/f/I.ric/BoWh-18-Cum-2021/GB	OQ436998
A.pha/f/I.ric/n_5/Cod-5-Dev-2021/GB	OQ436999
A.pha/f/I.ric/n_5/Cod-7-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437000
A.pha/f/I.ric/n=5/Cod-32-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437001
A.pha/f/I.ric-Dar-21-Devon-2021/GB	OQ437002
A.pha/f/I.ric-Exm15-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437003
A.pha/m/I.ric/n=5/Cod-4-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437004
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-9-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437005
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-12-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437006
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-17-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437007

Sequence_ID	Accession_number
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-23-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437008
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-26-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437009
A.pha/n/I.ric/n_10/Cod-28-Dev-2021/GB	OQ437010
A.pha/O.ari-S029-2023/GB	OQ437011
A.phag/O.ari-S03401-2023/GB	OQ437012

Nucleotide sequences obtained from this study were name using pathogen (*A. phagocytophilum*) name, sequence source/host and the year samples were collected etc. as below: A.pha. (*Anaplasma phagocytophilum*); h1 or h2.B.tau (heifer1 or 2, *Bos taurus*); f.B.tau (female, *Bos taurus*); f.I.ric (female, *Ixodes ricinus*), O.ari (*Ovis aries*); n1 or n2/I.ric (nymph, *Ixodes ricinus*); C.ela. (*Cervus elaphus*); n = x means pooled samples, C.cap (*Capreolus capreolus*).

Additional file 3: Table S2: A summary of NCBI online custom BLASTn search containing list of nucleotide sequences obtained from GB livestock, *I. ricinus* and deer species, GenBank accession numbers and percentage identity, established ecotypes based on recent literature, host and country of origin.

Sequence Id	Accession numbers matched	No of sequences matched	Ecotype	Accession host/country	Percentage (%) identity
A.pha./f/I.ric-M13.2/GBseq14-A.pha/C.cap-M413-2021/GB	KM215256 (all 4 matched)	4	II	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Slovenia	99.8
	JN005745		II	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Poland	
A.pha./f/I.ric-M13.3/GBseq13-A.pha/C.cap-M0404-2023/GB	DQ779568		II	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Poland	
	AF383226		II	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Switzerland	
A.pha./f/I.ric-Pem-6-2021/GB	KJ832471	2	I	<i>Equus caballus</i> /France	99.8
A.pha/C.ela-Nor405-2021/GB	U96729		I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /GB	
A.pha./f/I.ric-Pem-7-2021/GB	KJ832476	4	I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	100
A.pha/f/B.tau-316672-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/f/I.ric-Dar-21-Devon-2021/GB					
A.pha/f/I.ric-Exm15-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha./h1/B.tau-Dev-2021/GB	KJ832478	8	I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	100
A.pha./n1/I.ric-Cor-2021/GB					
A.pha./n2/I.ric-Cor-2021/GB					
A.pha./f/I.ric/n=5/Cod-32-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha./f/B.tau-103-Cor-2021/GB					
A.pha./f/B.tau-169b-2023/GB					
A.pha./f/B.tau-229b-2023/GB					
A.pha./f/B.tau-255-2023/GB					
A.pha./O.ar-100857-Dor-2021/GB	MG670108 (identical to both)	2	I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Poland	99.8
A.pha/C.ela-Nor408-2021/GB					
	KJ832473		I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	
.pha/B.tau-C315970-2023/GB	KJ832474	2	I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	100
A.pha/O.ari-S029-2023/GB					
A.pha/B.tau-C316672-2023/GB	KM215264	1	I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Slovenia	99.8
	U96730		I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /GB	
A.pha/B.tau-C316675-2023/GB	KJ622307	1	I	<i>Ursus arctos</i> /Slovenia	99.8
A.pha./f/I.ric/n=5/Cod-29-Dev-2021/GB	KJ832483	2	I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	100
A.pha./f/B.tau-329-2023/GB					
A.pha./f/B.tau-089-2023/GB	AF478552	2	I	<i>Cervus elaphus</i> Slovenia	100
A.pha./f/B.tau-317934-2023/GB					
A.pha./h2/B.tau-Dev-2021/GBseq18-013b-2023-GB	KJ832487/	17	I	<i>Bos taurus</i> /France	100
A.pha./f/B.tau-32b-2023/GB	KJ832484				
A.pha./f/B.tau-292d-2023/GB	AF548385		I	<i>Ovis aries</i> /Norway	

Sequence Id	Accession numbers matched	No of sequences matched	Ecotype	Accession host/country	Percentage (%) identity
A.pha/f/B.tau-308-2023/GB					
A.pha/f/B.tau-343b-2023/GB					
A.pha/f/B.tau-343c-2023/GB					
A.pha/f/I.ric/BoWh-18-Cum-2021/GB					
A.pha/f/I.ric/n_5/Cod-5-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/f/I.ric/n_5/Cod-7-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/m/I.ric/n=5/Cod-4-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-9-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-23-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/n/I.ric/n=10/Cod-26-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/n/I.ric/n_10/Cod-28-Dev-2021/GB					
A.pha/f/b.tau-309b-2023/GB	MF061233	1	I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /Slovenia	99.9
	JN656296		I	<i>Canis familiaris</i> /Finland	
A.pha/f/B.tau-483-2021/GB	KJ832463	1	I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> /France	98.9
	GQ452227		I	<i>Capra aegagrus</i> /Switzerland	
A.phag/O.ari-S03401-2023/GB	U96735	1	I	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> Switzerland	100
Total		48			

Additional file 4: Table S3. List of GenBank nucleotide accession numbers used for NCBI online BLASTn search.

AB454079,AF033101,AF172158,AF192796,AF383226,AF478552,AF482760,AF548385,AY219849,AY220467,AY529489,AY848747,DQ088133,DQ680012,DQ779568,EF647585,EU157921,EU839853,EU860087,EU982549,GQ452225,GQ452227,GQ988754,GQ988755,GQ988774,HM057223,HM057224,HQ630615,HQ630617,JF494833,JF494834,JF893915,JN005744,JN005745,JN055359,JN055360,JN656296,JN935930,KC583431,KC753762,KC800984,KF015601,KF031385,KF383228,KF383230,KF569921,KF569925,KF745743,KF745744,KF836094,KJ622307,KJ677107,KJ832449,KJ832450,KJ832462,KJ832463,KJ832464,KJ832468,KJ832469,KJ832470,KJ832471,KJ832473,KJ832474,KJ832475,KJ832476,KJ832478,KJ832480,KJ832481,KJ832482,KJ832483,KJ832484,KJ832485,KJ832487,KM215253,KM215254,KM215256,KM215257,KM215258,KM215259,KM215260,KM215261,KM215262,KM215263,KM215264,KM215265,KM215266,KR092132,KT192430,KT220191,KT220192,KT220193,KT970678,KT970679,KT970680,KU519284,KU519285,KU519286,KU712098,KU712104,KU712105,KU712108,KU712117,KU712127,KU863662,KY379956,LC334016,MF061233,MG570466,MG670108,U96727,U96728,U96729,U96730,U96735,EU157920,KU712123,HQ630619

Additional file 5: Table S4. List of published nested PCR primers (A), reaction volumes and thermal cycling conditions (B) used for the amplification *Anaplasma phagocytophilum groEL* gene in this study (Alberti et al., 2005)

A					
PCR round	Primer name	Nucleotide sequence	Product length (kb)	Annealing temperature (AT)	
First	Ephpl <i>groEL</i> (569)	5'-ATGGTATGCAGTTTGATCGC-3'	624 bp	56 °C	
	Ephpl <i>groEL</i> (1193)	5'-TCTACTCTGTCTTTGCGTTC-3'			
Second	Ephpl <i>groEL</i> (569)	5'-ATGGTATGCAGTTTGATCGC-3'	530 bp	60 °C	
	Ephl <i>groEL</i> (1142)	5'-TTGAGTACAGCAACACCACCGGAA-3'			
B					
<i>Anaplasma phagocytophilum</i> PCR mix			Nested <i>Anaplasma Phagocytophilum</i> PCR thermal cycling conditions		
Reagents	25 µl X1	Final conc.	PCR cycle	Temperature	Time
Nuclease free water	8.5 µl		• Initial denaturation	94 °C	10 min
2x iTaq universal Sybr mix	12.5 µl		Follow by 40 cycles:		
Forward primer	1 µl	0.4 µM	• Denaturation	94 °C	30 s
Reverse primer	1 µl	0.4 µM	• Annealing (start)	AT	30 s
Subtotal	23 µl		• Extension	72 °C	1 min
Template DNA	2 µl		Followed by:		
Total reaction volume	25 µl		• Final extension	72 °C	5 min
			• End temperature	4 °C	

Abbreviations

A. phagocytophilum: *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*; B.tau: *Bos taurus*; I.ric: *Ixodes ricinus*; O.ari: *Ovis aries*; C.ela: *Cervus elaphus*; C.cap: *Capreolus capreolus*; EDTA: Ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid (blood anticoagulant); GB: Great Britain; B.tau: *Bos taurus*

